

Historical Implications of Second Culture Acquisition

Dr. Zaheda Sultana

Associate Professor of English
Department of English
Government Degree College Khairatabad, Hyderabad
zahedasultana11@gmail.com

R. Sucharita

Lecturer
Department of English
Government Degree College Khairatabad, Hyderabad
sucharitha.repudi@gmail.com

Introduction

Culture is a very broad, intricate network of complexities. When the Council of Europe produced a list of learner competencies useful to know a language, it revealed that to know a language, in addition to grammatical competence, the learner, who aims to be culturally competent, needs socio-linguistic competence, socio-cultural and inter-cultural knowledge. Any cultural knowledge means extensive knowledge of that culture.

The role of culture in the second language learning is an area of emerging research. Similarly the Second Culture Acquisition (SCA) has attracted interest in the linguistic pedagogy. Its role and limitations are presented in this paper with the belief that a learner inherently has previous cultural knowledge of his or her own.

Historical Background

In the beginning of 20th century a research in the Amerindian languages revealed that thoughts, abstract notions and language are interrelated and these relationships are complex. In 1920's, Edward Sapir concluded that,

A language and the culture of its speakers cannot be analyzed in isolation. Language can be seen as a way to describe and represent human experience and understanding of the world, and members of a language community share systems of beliefs and assumptions which underlie their constructions of the world. ¹

Sapir also noted that all language behaviours have extremely complex patterns which are interconnected inextricably. Though languages have specific grammatical features, it is constraining to define these distinguishing features in terms of lexico-grammatical rules. The Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis of linguistic relativity looks beyond the abstract notions of lexico-grammatical rules.

Further developments in the specialized domains of Sociology, Linguistics and Anthropology have redefined culture. In *The Interpretation of Cultures*, Geertz notes that language and the uses of the language in a group form an interesting study for Social Anthropologists as they form an important part of human behaviour that denotes symbolic actions with respect to social structure and interactions within the community. He adds that human behaviour reflects culture and determines the use of language to communicate.² The study of the language use will enhance the understanding of their world of concepts and help in comprehension of cultural parameters within which the members of the group operate. As concepts, beliefs and identities are mostly revealed through the medium of languages, culture theory also concerns itself with the patterns of social and linguistic behaviours. The culture theory views language as an intricate network that represents what human behaviours mean and how they are expressed.

From 1960s work was carried out in the investigation of the connection between language and culture by Hymes, Kaplan and E. Hall in the areas such as interactional sociolinguistics, rhetorical patterns accepted in different cultures, behavioural and cognitive constructs respectively.

Definition of Culture

The term “culture” has been defined in various ways in different circumstances and disciplines. The best known definition of culture is provided by the Dutch psychologist Clifford Geertz as follows:

Historically transmitted semiotic network constructed by humans and which allows them to develop, communicate and perpetuate their knowledge, beliefs and attitudes about the world.³

Culture is a phenomenon which is never static. It is constantly evolving as people go about their lives on an everyday basis. It also consists of the knowledge that is shared among people which is visible in the actions, occupations and interpretations of their experience in a specified situation. This shared knowledge denotes both spoken and written communication that helps in understanding the message. However, even with the same language there may be other psychological or socio-cultural factors like appropriacy which has been recently realized. This realization has revived interest in the study of the connection between the language and culture.

Culture: A Multidimensional Concept

It is significant that any culture has two components. The macro-culture or big-C culture and micro-culture which can also be called small-c culture. The macro-culture is comparatively easy to study as it entails factual information about the fine arts, tourism, theatre and films. The micro culture, on the contrary, constitutes a complex variety of aspects, most of them interconnected. They include assumptions, beliefs, attitudes, values, behaviours, customs, norms, relationships, rituals, conventions of politeness, patterns of conversations, discourse organization, the concept of time, the marking of physical space and body language; and, the most important constituent of this aspect is verbal language. This micro-culture is imbibed by the individuals from birth; deeply entrenched in their sub-conscious and visible only in contrast with another culture. The micro-culture is non-tangible, works beneath the surface of the speakers' consciousness and enormously influences the way people think and behave. It determines the expectations and interprets the behaviour of other people linguistically and non-linguistically. Misunderstanding of both verbal and non-verbal communication results in the formation of distorted image of the native-speaker's society and culture.

Culture - More than "Four F's"

In the early 90's, Thomas and Kramsch noted that many language classrooms frequently reduce culture to "food, fairs, folklore and statistical facts."⁴ They emphasized that the impact of the culture on language learning and its use is far more complex than "the four F's" and that the research needs to link language teaching to culture. It is probably too simplistic to assume that culture can be evaluated, taught and understood through exercises

for reading news paper headlines and advertisements for jobs. Though customs, cuisine and courtesies can serve as an initiation to more in-depth discussions, they cannot address the impact of culture on a learner's linguistic and interactive behaviour.

Second Culture Acquisition - A Mirage

Second Culture Acquisition (SCA) in the language pedagogy has evoked interest as can be seen from a statement by Robinson Stuart and Nocon.

Regarding culture teaching and learning: together, these elements reflect a current direction which is recognizing the importance of second culture acquisition.⁵

But, whether cultural acquisition can be equated with the linguistic development is debatable. Byram terms the idea of teacher-led classroom tutoring as “vicarious”⁶ and rejects the notion of the teaching assuming that the “learners can acquire alien cultural concepts, values and behaviours, as if they were a *tabula rasa*.”⁷

Even in the case of study abroad programmes the development of the cross cultural understanding is not visible. According to Kramsch even those individuals who migrate to a new country and spend the rest of their lives as active participants in a new culture frequently feel “not really belonging to the host culture.”⁸

Although the immigrants develop an intellectual understanding and tolerance of other cultures, becoming cognitively similar to the members of the other culture without compromising their own identity is not possible. Though it is generally accepted that given sufficient time, exposure and motivation, adults can acquire second culture, it is important to understand what needs to happen if someone is to acquire this second culture. Hence, it is necessary to study the type of relationship between human mind and culture in the process of second culture acquisition.

References:

1. Sapir, Edward. *Culture, language, and personality*. Berkley: University of California Press, 1921.

2. Geertz, Clifford. *The Interpretation of Cultures*. New York: Basic Books, 1973, pp. 38-40.
3. Geertz, Clifford. *The Interpretation of Cultures*. New York: Basic Books, 1973, pp. 89.
4. Kramsch, Claire. "Culture in Language Learning; A view from the States." In K.de Bot, R. B. Ginsberg, & C. Kramsch (Eds.) , *Foreign Language Research in Cross Cultural Perspective*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 1991, pp. 216-235.
5. Robinson-Stuart, Gail., and Nocon, Honorine. "Second Culture Acquisition: Ethnography in the foreign Language Classroom." *Modern Language Journal*, vol.80, 1996, <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1996.tb05463.x/full>
6. Byram, Michael. *Cultural Studies in Foreign Language Education*. Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters, 1989, pp. 42.
7. Byram, Michael. "Teaching Culture and Language: Towards an Integrated Model." In D. Buttjes and M. Byram. (Eds.), *Mediating Languages and Cultures: towards an Intercultural Theory of Foreign Language Education*. Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters, 1991, pp.18.
8. Kramsch, Claire. "Language Study as Border Study: Experiencing Difference." *European Journal of Education*. (28 no.3), 1993b, pp. 349-358.